

Nature of Archaeological Records on Floodplain: A Geoarchaeological Interpretation of Wari-Bateshwar, Bangladesh

Muhammad Kamal Hossen Akanda¹, S. M. K. Ahsan², Swadhin Sen³

1.M. Phil Research Student, Department of Archaeology, Jahangirnagar University.

2. Professor, Department of Archaeology, Jahangirnagar University.

3. PhD Student and Assistant Professor, Department of Archaeology, Jahangirnagar University.

Although relatively less practiced and marginalized in the dominating brand of archaeology of Bangladesh, geoarchaeological approach has been playing crucial role in systematic and critically important research works. The aim of this paper is to apply some geoarchaeological field and laboratory methods for understanding the early historic archaeological records of Wari-Bateshwar. By identifying and analyzing vertical pattern of archaeological records in sedimentary and soil matrix in combination with map reading, satellite image interpretation, particle size distribution and chemical analyses of collected samples, it is found that archaeological records in different occurrences of Wari-Bateshwar have been reworked and relocated to a considerable extent. The findings also suggest that modifications of the archaeological materials have been engendered by locally occurred sheet floods and surface wash. Finally, it has been called for a greater and broader understanding of the 'flood culture' of past people living in the study area.

Problematization

The significance of this study lies in the approach of inquiry which incorporates an understanding of archaeological records not as 'objects in isolation', rather as phenomena in dynamic interaction with other immensely variable processes of alluvial environment. In this paper, an attempt has been made to understand and interpret the archaeological records of Wari-Bateshwar (see, for example, Pathan 1989, Chakrabarti 1992, Pawankar *et al.* 1998, Basa and Rahman 1998, Jahan 1999, Hoque *et al.* 2000, Ahmed 2001, Rahman *et al.* 2003, Akanda 2004) (figure 1) in reference to geomorphology, sedimentology and pedology of alluvial environment. This particular line of approach may provide comparatively wider and multivalent understanding of archaeological records in relation to their alluvial settings. As a consequence, construction of a frame of reference could be possible and thereby, it would be relatively easier to encounter widely established uncritical conclusions.

The archaeological records of Wari-Bateshwar occur in the floodplain. From both sedimentological and pedological perspective, floodplain is a very dynamic feature. It may subject to both catastrophic and gradual changes-erosion, deposition and stability-- over time. It has been proved by several alluvial geoarchaeological works that 'the

archaeological record of utilization of alluvial environments has in large part been shaped by the same processes that molded the alluvial stratigraphic record' (Waters 2000: 538, by citing Gardner and Donahue 1985, Waters 1992, Bettis and Hajic 1995, Ferring 1995, Mandel 1995, Brown 1997). Waters has further contended, 'deposition, erosion, and stability work in concert to preserve, arrange, and fragment the evidence of human activity associated with alluvial environments....As a result, no single alluvial stratigraphic sequence has a complete record of Quaternary sediments, soils and erosional unconformities, let alone a representative sample of archaeological record.' (Ibid. 539)

In Bangladesh, tectonic activities, continuous lateral

Fig. 1: Distribution of archaeological records in Wari-Bateshwar (the map has been prepared on the basis of the visible archaeological records only)

shifting of rivers and changes in their flow regime over time make it very difficult to construct the transformation of floodplain and the pedogenesis of floodplain soils. An understanding of the ensuing nature and pattern of archaeological records in floodplain environment becomes complex. Surface visibility and recovery of archaeological records are controlled by these processes to a considerable extent.

By taking these problems into account the objectives of the present study are:

1. To understand the nature of archaeological records in terms of geomorphological, geological and elementary pedological history of a floodplain.
2. To analyze vertical changes in the record as reflected by erosional and depositional contact in stratigraphy of their sedimentary and soil matrix supplemented by primary level understanding of horizontal changes through maps and visual interpretation of satellite image.
3. To recognize and analyze the influence of local fluvial environmental variables on deposition and modification of archaeological records.

Location

Wari and Bateshwar are two adjoining villages located about 4km southwest of Balabo Thana, Narsingdi district. Geocoordinate of two points in these two villages are: 24° 05' 46" North Lat./90°49' 42" East Long. and 24°05'34" North Lat./90°49' 40" East Long. Respectively (see Ahmed 2001:15). These two villages contain archaeological records the earliest date of which has tentatively been assigned to 4th-3rd century BC on the basis of stylistic dating of de-contextualized artifacts only.

Geomorphology

Local geomorphology could be described as follows:

Landforms

Two landform units namely Madhupur Tract and Old Brahmaputra Floodplain correspond to the alluvial environment of Wari-Bateshwar (see Islam 1991). (figure 2).

Madhupur Tract: Wari-Bateshwar area is located on the southeastern strip of Madhupur Tract. Some part of the Madhupur Tract have almost level, terrace like relief and much of the Madhupur Tract are closely dissected by valleys (Brammer 1996: 24). Chala (landforms with comparatively high convex slope gradient) and Byde (low valleys) are the main characteristics of the landform of this region. Thus, the landscape has an undulating relief. The occurrences of archaeological records have been recognized principally on slopes of chalas and on chalas those have been modified from a convex topography to a flat one by recent cultivation and other cultural activities (see Imran 2002:111).

Madhupur Tract is a tectonically uplifted surface, generally standing 10-20 feet above the adjoining floodplains. Compact clays, previously called Pleistocene clays, and now known as Madhupur Clays have formed it. It is believed to be equivalent in age to the Pleistocene (Rashid 1991, Soil Survey Report of Dhaka District 1965, Cited in Sen and Hoque 1999: 2). Yet, as our observation suggest, in many places Madhupur clay is overlain by recent flood deposits. Interestingly, archaeological records are found to occur in these recent flood sediments. If archaeological records are used as a chronological marker, then these flood sediments are supposed to be of late Holocene in age.

Old Brahmaputra Floodplain: The western part of Old Brahmaputra floodplain is another crucial component of Wari-Bateshwar alluvial environment. The soils are

formed from the sediments which are replenished every year by fresh deposition of silt carried down by the flood waters. This part of the Old Brahmaputra Floodplain which the river virtually abandoned when it moved into the Jamuna channel about 200 years ago has a generally smooth topography with broad ridges and basins. Ridges and basins are primary characterized by loamy soils and extensive areas of clays respectively. Relief and soil patterns are more irregular close to channels and include some areas with sandy soils (Brammer 1996: 64). Please, note that the delineation of

Fig. 2: Geomorphology of Wari-Bateshwar

Fig. 3: Distribution of sampling locations

the limit of this comparatively recent landform has been done by extent of inundation by the present channel.

Rivers and waterbodies

In Wari-Bateshwar area Old Brahmaputra river and Arial Khan river are the major channels now. Both of them have meandering style with moderate sinuosity. A small meandering stream locally known as *Kaira Khal* flows through relatively higher part of the valleys (figure 2). Besides, a few numbers of Beel (seasonally flooded bowl-shaped low lands or depressions) are located in this area. These are Dangir *Beel*, Chargachiar *Beel*, Belaba *Beel*, Wari *Beel*, etc.

The Old Brahmaputra flows through the southeast, Arial Khan flows through the east and Kaira Khal is located on the south of the area. The occurrences are 4 km. away from the supposed confluence of *Kaira Khal* and Arial Khan, although it was not possible to locate any geomorphic feature showing the sign of confluence.

It should be noted that the networks of *bydes* are seasonally flooded during the monsoon. Thereby, the *chalias* have an appearance of dispersed islands at that time.

Methodology

The methodological procedures which have been incorporated and followed in this study are primarily influenced by the general fieldwork framework proposed by Knudson (1978), Drewett (1999), and secondarily, by the selective appropriation of the particular field strategies by Waters (2000), Brown (1999), Butzer (1982), and Courty, Goldberg and Macphail (1989).

Various maps and geo-hydrological data (i.e. topographic maps, satellite images, base maps, drainage maps, etc.) were collected from different government and non-government organizations like Soil Resource Development Institute (SRDI), Centre for Environment and Geographical Information Service (CEGIS) and Local

Government and Engineering Department (LGED). A natural colour composite LandsatTM image of the region was collected from Mr. Masood Imran, who had previously collected it from CEGIS. At this stage we attempted to evaluate as much published and unpublished data as possible to formulate and solve our problems about the study area.

At the second step entire area was explored and some spots were selected (figure 3) to recognize the vertical pattern of the sedimentary and soil matrix, which have embedded archaeological materials and

which are of archaeological significance. Local geomorphology and topography were also considered in these selections. To save time and money, we usually selected the sections exposed by the local people. In other cases these sections were scraped by us. Except a few occasions we used a Garmin 12 GPS receiver to record the location of the section. After removing 10-15 cm recently weathered material from the surface of the section, we analyzed and recorded each section and delineated different units on sedimentological and pedological ground. Owing to complicity and contradictions in prevailing soil classification system in Bangladesh (i.e. between UNESCO/FAO and USDA systems) we avoided the understanding of sections as soil profiles. For the first two sections, samples were collected from each unit with soil sampling spoons. For the other sections, we recorded field description of different physical properties with the aid of systematic manual examination of texture and colour.

At the third stage, we performed sieving and pipette analyses following Folk (1968) for particle size analysis of the collected samples. In the laboratory of SRDI, manual of SRDI, Bray and Kurtz methods, Walkley and Black's (1934) Wet Oxidation Methods were followed to determine CaCO₃, Phosphorus and Total Carbon respectively and Metrohm 691 pH Meter was used for the measurement of pH.

Field Observation and Laboratory Analysis

We have recorded five sections from the study area. General physical properties of sediments, degree of pedogenesis and ferruginization and chemical analyses of some selected properties were the criteria for delineating different units. Presence, spatial patterning and frequency of archaeological records were also considered as variables in unit separation. We carried out particle size analysis and chemical analysis of the samples from two sections. Physical properties of other sections are described in the

present study.

Data regarding physical and chemical properties of the identified, recorded and analyzed sections are as follows:

Section 1 (figure 4 and 5)

Location: Wari, near Muluk Chan's House.

Landform: Terrace.

Relief: Flat

Parent material: Madhuur Clay and older aluvium

Physiography: Nearly level Madhupur Tract.

Moisture condition in profile: Moist.

Vegetation: Native grasses.

Total depth: 120 cm

Unit 1: (0-5 cm). Dark Yellowish Brown (10YR, 4/4), very fine sand. Poorly sorted.

Unit 2: (5-22 cm). Dark Greyish Brown (10YR, 4/2), very fine sand with potsherds. Poorly sorted.

Unit 3: (22-40 cm). Reddish Brown (2.5 YR, 4/3), very fine sand with potsherds. Poorly sorted.

Unit 4: (40-70 cm). Dark Brown (7.5YR, 3/3). Coarse silt with potsherds. Poorly sorted.

Unit 5: (70-95 cm). Dark Brown (7.5YR, 3/3), very fine sand with potsherds. Moderately sorted.

Table 1: Laboratory Data from Section 1

Location / Depth.	Graphic mean (M _z) in φ	Graphic Deviation (Q ₁) in φ	Skewness (S _k) in φ	Kurtosis (K _G) in φ	% of Sand, Silt & Clay	P ^H	Phosphorus	CaCO ₃	Total Carbon	Color
Wari. 10cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Strongly coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-49.42 Si-50.56 C- 0.02	5.2	43.9	1.0	0.77	10YR, 4/4, DYB
Wari. 15cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Strongly coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-43.91 Si-56.0 C-0.08	-	-	-	-	-
Wari. 30cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Nearly symmetrical	Leptokurtic	S-44.92 Si-53.60 C-1.48	5.3	55.88	1.5	0.49	10YR, 4/2, DGB
Wari. 50cm	Coarse silt	Poorly sorted	Strongly coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-33.80 Si-64.26 C-1.94	5.6	81.45	2.5	0.42	2.5YR, 4/3, RB
Wari. 70 cm	Very fine sand	Moderately sorted	Strongly coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-47.90 Si-52.04 C-0.06	5.6	82.32	1.5	0.35	7.5YR, 3/3, DB. 5YR, 4/4, RB
Wari. 90cm	Very fine sand	Moderately sorted	Coarse skewed	Very leptokurtic	S-35.70 Si-62.38 C-1.92	5.5	78.80	0.5	0.28	7.5YR, 3/3, DB.
Wari. 100 cm	Coarse silt	Poorly sorted	Coarse skewed	Very leptokurtic	S-45.16 Si-54.81 C-0.03	5.5	41.83	1.0	0.07	10 YR, 6/3, PB, 7.5YR, 5/3, B
Wari. 120cm	Coarse silt	Poorly sorted	Coarse skewed	Very leptokurtic	S- Si- C-	-	-	-	-	-

Fig. 4. Section 1

Fig. 5. Section 1:Wari, near Muluk Chan's House

Fig. 6: Lithologs of Granulometric data from section 1 (Left) & section 2 (Right)

Unit 6: (95-110cm). Pale Brown (7.5YR, 6/3). Very fine sand with a few Fe-Mn pellets. Moderately sorted.

Unit 7: (110-120 cm). Brown (7.5YR, 5/3). Coarse silt with very strong development of Fe-Mn pellets. Poorly sorted. There is sharp contact between unit 7 and 6.

Laboratory data has been presented in Table 1 and litholog of this section has been presented in figure 6

Section 2 (figure 7 and 8)

Location: Asham Rajar Garh, Bateshwar.

Landform: Terrace.

Relief: Convex

Parent material: Madhupur clay.

Moisture condition in profile: Fully moist.

Vegetation: Native grass.

Total depth: 180 cm

This section was an exposed portion of Asam Rajar Garh, an archaeological record which is believed to be an earthwork constructed by past people. This mud wall (?) is conventionally interpreted in taken for granted terms as early historic in age and contemporary to the occupation on the paleo landscape.

Unit 1: (0-8 cm) Dark Reddish Brown (2.5YR, 2.5/4) very fine sand. Poorly sorted.

Unit 2: (8-34 cm) Red (2.5YR, 4/6) very fine sand with a few iron pellets. Poorly sorted. Iron nodules and red sediment indicates that it is a result of oxidation.

Unit 3: (34-80 cm). Dark Red (2.5YR, 3/6) very fine sand with strong development of iron pellets. Moderately sorted.

Unit 4: (80-180 cm). Reddish Brown (2.5YR, 4/4) and Dark Red (10Y, 3/6 or 2.5YR, 3/6) very fine sand with very strong development of iron pellets. Moderately sorted. Dark Red colour indicates high rate of oxidation.

Laboratory data has been presented in Table 2 and litholog

Table 2: Laboratory Data from Section 2

Location / Depth.	Graphic mean (M _z) in φ	Graphic Deviation (Q ₁) in φ	Skewness (S _k) in φ	Kurtosis (K _G) in φ	% of Sand, Silt & Clay	P ^H	Phosphorus	CaCO ₃	Total Carbon	Color
ARG 05cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-37.34 Si-60.30 C-2.36	4.6	3.39	1.0	0.87	2.5YR, 2.5/4, DRB.
ARG 30cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Coarse skewed	Playtikurtic	S-51.86 Si-46.64 C-1.50					
ARG 50cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Strongly coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-45.12 Si-53.01 C-1.87	5.1	0.78	0.5	0.31	2.5YR, 4/6, R
ARG 70cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Strongly coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-35.71 Si-62.05 C-2.24					
ARG 115cm	Very fine sand	Moderately sorted	Coarse skewed	Leptokurtic	S-32.39 Si-65.97 C-1.64	5.1	0.48	0.5	0.31	2.5YR, 3/6, DR.
ARG 180cm	Very fine sand	Poorly sorted	Strongly coarse skewed	Very leptokurtic	S-27.71 Si-72.29 C-0.00	5.4	1.45	0.5	0.17	10R, 3/6, DR. 2.5YR,4/4, RB

Fig. 7. Section 2

Fig. 8. Section 2: Asham Rajar Garh, Bateshwar (without unit 4)

of section 2 has been shown in figure 6.

In spite of analyzing the soils and sediments of the two sections above, we have performed field examinations of a few other sections in later period when we went for a short field trip with Prof. S. N. Rajguru, former professor of geoarchaeology, Deccan College Post-Graduate Research Institute, Pune, India. Although the observations of these sections are not supported by any laboratory analysis, they could be of immense significance for our study. The characteristic and features of sections 3, 4, and 5 are given below:

Section 3 (figure 9 and 10)

Location: Asham Rajar Garh.

Total depth: 487 cm.

There are 5 units. There is distinct development of two generations of soil profile at the bottom part the colour of which grades from yellowish clayey silt to reddish silty clay. There is no blocky structure or pedality. Reddish soil is with incipient pedogenesis as indicated by Fe-Mn concretions and iron pellets. There is strong disconformity between top reddish soil and underlying hard compact red soil with distinct development of two generations of profile. The soils from the top part are uniform in texture and colour.

The disconformity suggests that overlying material is a result of old flood system or it could be anthropogenic. In the upper part the materials is uniform in texture and no elements of coarser things as brick bats are present (Rajguru, personal communication).

Section 4 (figure 11 and 12)

Location: Wari, near Rashid Master's House.

Total depth: 230cm.

There are 4 units. Colluvial debris, indicated by its sharp contact with unit 3, with rich occurrence of potsherd has been observed in unit 2. The potsherds got deposited on Madhupur Clay. The entire section suggests a degradation of the site. The colluvium with pottery has also been hardened without any strong development soil profile. The bottom most unit is a typical example of oxisol.

Section 5 (figure 13 and 14)

Location: Wari, near Muslem Mia's house.

Total depth: 265cm.

There are 4 units. A disturbed garbage pit with bedding of potsherds has been observed in unit 2. The potsherds are in semi primary context as the contact of this unit with pit at the bottom is sharp and the frequency of potsherds is also

Fig.9:Section 3

Fig. 10. Section 3: Asham Rajar Garh

Fig. 11: Section 4

Fig. 12. Section 4: Wari, near Rashid Master's House

Fig. 13: Section 5

Fig. 14. Section 5: Wari, near Muslim Mia's House

different. Unit 3 is grayish ash clay with a pit dug by past people. Charcoal has also been observed in this layer. Unit 4 is reddish silty caly with strong development of Mn pellets and corresponds to Madhupur clay.

Interpretation

A few numbers of potsherds were found to be embedded within the matrix of unit 2, 3, 4 and 5 of section 1. The contact between the units (except between 6 and 7) is gradational. It could be assumed that there were no drastic changes in depositional environment of these units. But the sharp contact between unit 6 and 7 is very significant as it denotes drastic change. The degree of pedogenesis is much higher in unit 7 than unit 6. The amount, colour and hardness of Mn-Fe pellets and degree of ferruginization infers to the higher degree of soil formation in a relatively stable environment. The amount of organic carbon and calcium carbonate supports this interpretation. We think that this unit corresponds to the landform which is conventionally designated as Madhupur Track.

The upper units (unit 1-6) are relatively homogenous in terms of matrix, though there are a few potsherds in units 2-5. There is evidence of weak pedogenesis in unit 6 indicated by Fe-Mn pelletization. But the units above do not show any signature of pedogenesis. The particle size distribution and sorting indicate that these units were deposited in a fluvial environment with moderate to low energy regime. However, the sharp contact might indicate a sudden change in the deposition pattern, probably with a flush flood of low capacity. The difference among unit 5-6 could be the result of the variations in the flood regimes which might have varied on seasonal and energy level basis. We think the most interesting point here the presence of potsherds in units 2-5. The amount, frequency and spatial matrix of these cultural records indicate that most probably they are locally transported colluvial materials. The inference of Hassan (1978:202) - "A sediment formed from the sudden dumping of sedimentary materials will be poorly sorted. A weak surface runoff will wash out heterogeneous materials and also form a poorly sorted colluvial deposits." - supports this interpretation. It could be said on the basis of these evidences that present location of these potsherds is a result of sudden dumping of sedimentary materials. The sharp contact between 6 and 7

thus becomes more meaningful on the ground that sometime in the past these potsherds were locally transported from a primary or semi-primary location to be deposited on exposed surface of unit 7.

There is further evidence in support of our argument. This section is an interesting example of two coarsening upward cycle (from 120- 50 cm and 50-0 cm), which is oppositional to the fining upward cycle of floodplain sedimentary facies deposited by regular floods. Sudden change of flood in terms of capacity, volume and intensity owing to gradual shifting of channels or shallowing of water levels might contribute to a coarsening upward cycle. The depositional environment as suggested by Hassan (1978: 202, 206) and Reineck and Singh (1980) from the textural classification of the sediments (Sandy-silt and Silty-sand) and positive skewness also signifies a floodplain deposited in a low energy regime. Fe-Mn segregation at the bottom of unit 6 might be due to rapid downward movement of the water.

The comments of J-P. Bravard could be of extreme significance at this point of our discussion. He opines, '[these soils] are characterized by a strong leaching to the detriment of the former material, which may be explained by their position up the Pleistocene terrace' (2005, Personal communication). His comments along with our analysis of section 1 strongly suggest that the soils and sediments have undergone substantial reworking during post-depositional phases.

Visual interpretation of a LandsatTM composite image of first 3 bands (winter season 1997) (figure 15) shows several signatures of paleochannels and channel remnants on Old Brahmaputra floodplain (figure 2). Besides, there are a few bowl-shaped depressions which are seasonally flooded and basically, they corresponds to the valley along with the other valleys in the area. It seems that both neotectonic activities and lateral shifting of rivers are responsible for the patterns of erosions and depositions that affected the formation of these particular geomorphic features. Although it is not possible to determine the exact chronology and pattern of channel migrations with the

available evidence, the changes in local fluvial regime could be attested by the presence of them. There by, shifts in the intensity and nature of flood were most probable during the past 3000 years and they might have the principle agent in relocation and modification of archaeological records in the region.

On the other hand, the entire section 2 of Asam Rajar Garh is strongly pedogenized and degree of pedogenization is almost homogenous throughout. It has been mentioned earlier that this section contains Fe-Mn nodules. These nodules are formed by

Fig. 15: Natural colour composite image of Wari-Bateshwar region

reduction and solution of Fe under anaerobic conditions and their subsequent oxidation and deposition in aerobic zones.

The graphic mean values shows the overall size of the sediment of Asham Rajar Garh is very fine sand, which along with positive skewness suggest that the sediment, was originated from low energy fluvial environment (Reineck and Singh 1980:137). The values of Standard Deviation indicate that the maximum sediments were poorly sorted and it may be pinpointing to the fluvial origin of sediments.

However, the uniformity of texture and pedogenization throughout the section is quite suggestive. As it has been told before that there are two interpretations regarding origin of Asam Rajar Garh. One interpretation assumes that the Garh is cultural in origin and the other has contested this prevailing assumption regarding its function and time (Imran 2001: 118). But the later interpretation does not suggest that this garh is natural in origin. Rather this interpretation has identified the former one as taken for granted assumption and eventually, asked for a rethinking.

But with the analyses of the section 2, it is not possible to find testimony for either of the interpretation. On one hand, we have strongly and uniformly pedogenized silty-sand which is poorly sorted. It could have been dumped and uniformity in ferruginization might be a result of pre-oxidized character of the parent material, known as Madhupur Clay. On the other hand, in absence of any sharp contact between the paleolandscape and the *garh*, it is not possible to say with relative certainty and accuracy that this feature, which is quite long in length and is a sudden change in the flat and monotonous landscape, is a signature of cultural activity. The high degree of oxidation might also be a result of re-pedogenesis of the eroded and deposited parent materials.

Chemical analyses of the sediment from section 1 and 2 indicate that values of pH are low, along with the values of CaCO₃, P, and C. Bravard (2005, personal communication) has suggested, 'the C content shows diffusion to the bottom of the profile, probably from forest remnants. The very low value of pH of Wari could be explained by the position on the surface. On the other hand, as soils from Asam Rajar Garh section were taken from closer to the rim of the high terrace like feature (or earth work), may have been partly eroded, which could explain a higher value of pH (lower leaching)'.

The field and laboratory data from the soils and sediments of Asam Rajar Garh overtly challenges the taken for granted assumption. Section 2 and 5 offer two completely different pictures of depositional environment. However, it is not possible to falsify the prevailing assumption without further analyses. As was opined by Rajguru, past people might also have used earlier natural feature, in this case an uplifted terrace, to construct an earthwork. Therefore, we have three probabilistic inferences for the origin of Asam Rajar Garh, all of which are equally valid at this moment on geoarchaeological ground.

Another interesting point to be noted is that the surface visibility and recovery of archaeological records in this area must have been controlled to a greater extent by alluvial environmental variables which are the agents of principle processes of archaeological record formation (see Terrenato and Ammerman 1996 see the relation between geomorphological variables and surface visibility of archaeological records).

Results and propositions

Most of the reported archaeological records from Wari-Bateshwar are surface collection. A considerable number of artifacts have also been found from digging, though these artifacts have been presented and published without any systematic stratigraphic, in terms of archaeological, geoarchaeological and pedological, reference. The nature of the evidence, thus, prohibits any further critical interpretation regarding their contextual association in particular. Furthermore, conclusions derived from these artifacts have been prone to spurious speculations (Imran 2002: 113).

What we have found in our present study, despite their limitations in reaching anything conclusive because of the sample size and complexity in the nature of the evidence, is vital for understanding of Wari-Bateshwar in its entirety. The results could be summarized as follows:

- Archaeological records of Wari-Bateshwar, as they were found to be occurred in the studied sections, have been reworked and relocated probably due to combination of recurring sheet floods and surface wash. As a consequence of the formation, their present spatial occurrences are the result of locally generated colluvial depositions. However, the modifications by the floods might not have been very intense as it is testified by the in situ occurrences of pits and their contents (i.e. ash) on section 5.
- Asam Rajar Garh, despite its prevailing identification as an earthwork contemporary to the occupation in the area, could either be a natural feature created by strong to moderate flood of paleo-fluvial system, or be a human modification and manipulation of advantageous relief of alluvial landscape.
- Fluvial processes, floods in particular, have been crucial in post-depositional phase of the formation processes of archaeological records. Occurrence of records in comparatively recent weakly pedogenized or non-pedogenized alluvium in every case is a firm evidence in support of this postulation. Ever changing matrix of archaeological records thus clearly indicates that the artifacts are mostly semi-primary or completely relocated (i.e. secondary, tertiary, etc.) in nature. Evidence of the migratory patterns of adjacent rivers also indicates to the importance of understanding flood history for this very

Pratnatattva

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